

NECESSITY OF ELECTRONIC PASSPORT IN THE DIGITAL SYSTEM

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"The concept of the development of the digital economy of Turkmenistan for 2019-2025" attaches particular importance to the widespread integration of the digital system in the country. In this regard, the tasks defined in the "Program of socio-economic development of the country of the President of Turkmenistan for 2019-2025", developed on the basis of the initiatives of Turkmen leader, are key importance. With the transition to the digital system, documents have been kept electronically in the country. State regulation should also be noted when using digital electronic documents. When electronic documents are used, state regulatory work is carried out by the Cabinet of Ministers of Turkmenistan and other state institutions in accordance with their powers [1].

State regulatory work to implement a unified state policy when electronic documents are used; to ensure the rights and legal interests of users of electronic documents; to legally ensure the technology of creating, processing, storing, issuing and receiving electronic documents; and develop a safe and secure payment system using electronic documents; is aimed at ensuring the security and protection of data when it is created, developed, stored, transmitted and received [2].

There are more than 140 States and non-state entities (e.g. United Nations, European Union) currently issuing e-Passports, and over 1 billion e-Passports in circulation. E-Passports add a layer of security to traditional non electronic passports by embedding an electronic chip in the passport booklet that stores the biographical information visible on page 2 of the passport, as well as a digital security feature. This digital security feature is a country specific "digital signature." These digital signatures are unique and can be verified using their respective certificates [3].

The e-passport is also the cornerstone of the digital system. An electronic passport (identity card of a citizen) is an electronic document proving the identity of a citizen. This is an electronic medium containing personal information necessary for identification. It is a plastic card containing a chip with the size of a bank card. Moreover, except the standard passport information, fingerprints and other biometric authentication information, driver's license, migration card and electronic signature can be recorded. The integration of an electronic passport provides with the creation of a single electronic database of documents, including cloud storage and access, as well as addressing security issues. Cryptographic protection of SIM cards when using the software on mobile devices. Crypto protection and issuing secure national SIM cards should be addressed. Transactions with an electronic passport will also be possible through the "My Passport" mobile phone application. It is to provide online access to personal data, in particular, with the help of an e-passport in the form of a mobile application. This document, in particular, creates a legal basis for creating a digital profile of citizens and legal entities, an electronic identity document that creates conditions for the development and entry into the field of electronic services, commerce and other transactions conducted in electronic form [4].

Currently, tests are being carried out on the preparation of the digital passport system project, its main parts - electronic reading and placement of its electronic data, electronic signature and biometric image, and ensuring the protection of personal information.

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